

Distributed Ledger Technology based Machine-to-Machine Economy: Parking Payment System for Autonomous Vehicle

(Ekonomi Mesin-ke-mesin berasaskan Teknologi Lejar Teragih: Sistem Pembayaran Parkir Kenderaan Autonomi)

Kwan James Ding, Jit Singh Mandeep, Mohammad Tariqul Islam

*“Electronic Engineering Programme,
Faculty of Engineering & Built Environment, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Malaysia*

ABSTRACT

The main idea behind Autonomous Vehicle (AV) is to reduce or remove human intervention during transportation, these includes payments such as toll fees, parking fees and others. In other words, AV also aims at establishing a Machine-to-Machine (M2M) economy. Internet-of-Things (IoT) will play a big part in enabling AV to establish high-speed, resilient, low-latency and connectivity especially in the payment system and data exchange between machines hence resulting in a fully autonomous system for the M2M economy. Our current payment system which is centralized in nature do not meet the requirement for M2M economy as transaction fees, lack of transparency and slow transactions deemed to be ineffective. In this paper, Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT)-based system for M2M economy is introduced for ensuring effective M2M transactions which securely process the payments. This paper also provides an introduction and application of an alternative DLT which is the IOTA's ledger, “The Tangle”, as it offers the suitable features that are required to establish a M2M micropayment system. Besides, the edge centric IoT or fog computing, where the supernodes process and transmit collected data from individual nodes directly to both centralized and decentralized database is preferred over the cloud centric IoT, where individual nodes simply aggregate and transmit data to a centralized cloud. The reason of this proposed implementation is to increase the overall responsiveness, reliability and efficiency for the IoT system used in the M2M ecosystem.

Keywords: Distributed Ledger Technology; M2M economy; Internet of Things, IOTA

ABSTRAK

Idea utama di sebalik Kenderaan Autonomi (AV) adalah untuk mengurangkan atau menghapuskan intervensi manusia semasa perjalanan, ini termasuk bayaran seperti tol, yuran letak kereta dan lain-lain. Dengan kata lain, AV juga bertujuan mewujudkan ekonomi Mesin-ke-Mesin (M2M). Internet-of-Things (IoT) akan memainkan peranan besar dalam membolehkan AV mewujudkan kelajuan tinggi, berdaya tahan, latensi rendah dan penyambungan terutamanya dalam sistem pembayaran dan pertukaran data antara mesin sehingga menghasilkan sistem autonomi sepenuhnya dalam ekonomi M2M. Sistem pembayaran pada masa ini yang bersifat terpusat tidak memenuhi syarat untuk ekonomi M2M kerana yuran transaksi, kekurangan ketelusan dan transaksi lambat yang dianggap tidak efektif. Dalam penyelidikan ini, sistem berdasarkan Teknologi Ledger Teragih (DLT) untuk ekonomi M2M diperkenalkan untuk memastikan transaksi M2M berkesan yang memproses pembayaran dengan selamat. Penyelidikan ini juga memperkenalkan dan mengaplikasikan sebuah DLT alternatif iaitu lejar IOTA, yang disebut “The Tangle” kerana ia menawarkan ciri-ciri diperlukan untuk menubuhkan sebuah sistem pembayaran mikro M2M. Selain itu, IoT edge-centric atau pengkomputeran fog dimana setiap supernode memproses dan menghantar data yang dikumpul daripada setiap node individu terus ke pangkalan data terpusat dan terdesentralisasi akan digunakan untuk menggantikan IoT cloud-centric, di mana setiap node individu yang mengagregat dan menghantar data ke cloud yang terpusat. Sebab implimentasi yang dicadang ini adalah untuk meningkatkan daya tindak, kebolehpercayaan dan kecekapan dalam sistem IoT yang digunakan dalam ekosistem M2M.

Kata Kunci: Teknologi Lejar Teragih, ekonomi M2M, Internet of Things, IOTA

INTRODUCTION

It is clear that the emergent of Internet of Things (IoT) is already having a significant impact on today's industry. IoT is the catch-all term used to describe machine-to-machine (M2M) connectivity (Internet & Intelligence 2016). The M2M communication is enabled by data exchanges among the machines, resulting in valuable data streams. The amount of data produced can be used to further improve existing services or even create new services. This significantly benefits various industries especially industries with high level of automation such as the AV industry.

Most IoT platforms today such as Azure, AWS, and IBM Watson are built around cloud-centric IoT architecture via device-to-cloud communication (Corsaro 2016). As number of IoT devices are scaling up exponentially according to a Gartner report which the total will reach 25 billion by 2021, immense volume of data will continue to be produced by these devices indefinitely ("Gartner Identifies Top 10 Strategic IoT Technologies and Trends" n.d.). Unfortunately, the cloud-centric IoT provides cloud computing at a remote and far end network from the nodes, which is infeasible in many application scenarios (Yeow et al. 2018). For instance, IoT in the AV industry where translating information on the road and decision making must be process in real-time with low latency and high throughput. Henceforth, the IoT system used in this paper is shifted towards edge centric IoT as these processes are performed at the edge network which is near where the data is generated.

Although IoT in general especially M2M solutions are already disrupting businesses and existing industrial landscape, there are a few issues arises from this approach such as data safety and monetization issues on data streams and services. In current architecture of the IoT networks, validation of transmission in any forms of data generally require a central authority to generate trust between these exchanges. This is especially true when digital monetary transactions are involved within the M2M ecosystem. Having a third party to validate these transactions not only causes scalability issues but also threatens the confidentiality, integrity and availability of these transactions and services as this centralized architecture poses a high chance of single point failure by various types of attacks such as Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks (Weisenberger & de Knecht 2019).

Therefore, this paper introduces to the implementation of Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) as a potential solution for the mentioned challenges. The goal of a DLT system proposed by (Rauchs et al. 2018) is to produce a set of authoritative records that are validated and executed via a multi-party consensus process that involves multiple participants without any central authority. Unconfirmed transactions are created and broadcast

(i.e. proposals to make a new ledger entry), which get bundled together into records, and added to the ledger. These ledgers represent the globally agreed upon set of records which are collectively held by participants in the network, hence making them immutable. The feature of DLTs which includes the combination of cryptocurrencies (tokens) and M2M communication paves the way for the so-called M2M economy (Momtaz 2020). Due to the underlying DLT, all forms of data, such as tokens, messages or raw data itself, can be transferred from one device to another without the intervention of physical individual (GSMA 2018).

Although DLTs solves many of today's digital monetary transactions issues, however they exhibit some other forms of restriction which depends on the design of the DLT. The PoW of the Bitcoin-Blockchain is an example of a resource and time demanding security mechanism. In addition, low throughput of Bitcoin-Blockchain is due to the difficulty of PoW which the maximum size of a block is set to 1 Mb, further limiting the amount of data being transmitted (Conoscenti et al. 2016). Therefore, its energy and time demanding security mechanism of the Bitcoin-Blockchain makes the technology poorly suitable for systems that require high throughput and scalability such as the IoT systems.

These limitations on the Bitcoin-Blockchain could be inhibit by using an alternate design approach which is the directed acyclic graph (DAG) method used by IOTA. To issue a new transaction on its ledger, "The Tangle", users must work to approve two other transactions made which are allotted by its tip selection algorithm. By doing so the initiator of the new transaction indirectly confirms the validity of a subsection of the Tangle hence contributing to the network's security (Popov 2018). This results in eliminating transaction fees as no miners needed to validate new transactions instead it is done by the issuer themselves with significantly lesser amount of PoW needed.

This paper aims at identifying the suitable technologies to envision a scalable, transparent and secure M2M economy. Next, to design and implement a parking payment system for autonomous vehicle as a Proof of Concept (PoC) DLT based M2M economy. Finally examine and analyze the properties of the IOTA transaction structure used in the transaction made in the proposed PoC.

METHODOLOGY

Hardware Aspect

The hardware of the proposed implementation consists of:

Raspberry pi4 and Raspberry Pi Zero microcontrollers which will function as the edge modules or IoT nodes that provides the ability to receive and update data and status of devices and vehicles via HTTP requests. The edge servers maintain connections to the system’s database during initialization phase. When a new data log is introduced to the system, the log is imported via a POST request into the system’s database. It can then be translated and served by the web server to the end user applications.

Green and Red LED lights will be used to indicate parking status. If the parking lot is empty, the Green LED light will be turned on. If the parking lot has been parked by a vehicle, the Red LED light will be turned on.

Ultrasonic Sensor (HC-SR04) is used to measure the distance between the sensor and the object. The sensor acts as a parking device where vehicle will park in front of it. The distance of the object is calculated from Equation 1 where d is the distance of the object from the sensor; t is the total time from transmitter to receiver and v is the velocity of sound which is 340 m / s at room temperature.

$$d = v * t/2 \quad \dots(1)$$

1kΩ and 2kΩ resistors are used as voltage dividers to reduce the voltage from the 5V of the HC-SR04 output pin to the 3.5 V input pin on the Pi as calculate as follows:

$$V_o = V_{in} \left(\frac{R_1}{R_1 + R_2} \right) \quad \dots(2)$$

$$= 5 \left(\frac{2000}{2000 + 1000} \right) = 3.33V$$

PiCamera is used to take pictures of vehicle number plate. Then, the number plate number is extracted by Pi using computer vision. Computer vision is implemented by importing the OpenALPR module into the parking device code. OpenALPR is an Automatic License Plate Recognition written in C ++ with binding in C #, Java, Node.js, and Python. The library analyzes photos and videos to identify the number plate of a vehicle. The final output is a vehicle license plate number in text form (“OpenALPR Documentation — openalpr 2.7.102 documentation” n.d.).

FIGURE 1. Schematic diagram of parking device

System Architecture

The architecture is built around five key activities: *Initialization Phase*; *Request Payment* and *Check*

Incoming Payment which are executed by parking devices; *Check Payment Request* and *Send Payment* which are executed by vehicles. These activities are illustrated in the flow charts in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

FIGURE 2. Flowchart of parking device executing *Request Payment* and *Check Incoming Payment*

FIGURE 3. Flowchart of vehicle executing *Check Payment Request* and *Send Payment*

RESTful Web Service Implementation

A RESTful web service is designed and developed to serve as an API to facilitate data between Edge devices, mobile or web applications and system databases. In this PoC, the REST API is built with Node.js and Express that interact with a SQLite

database. Express is a middleware that provides HTTP method utilities that manage every requests and response to an API endpoint. Node.js is a JavaScript runtime environment designed to develop scalable network applications by serving requests with low latency and high throughput. Finally, the SQLite database is used as the system’s database to store data of applications and devices. Figure 5 shows the block diagram implementation of these tools.

FIGURE 5. Communication between devices and applications to the database through the RESTful web service

Initialization Phase

When a new device (vehicle or parking device) is detected, the Edge server performs the initialization function to update the setup. The Edge server of the supernode will retrieve the new device data from the database via a GET request that previously

registered by their owners using the mobile or web application. The new device data is then stored in the local database of the supernode in a .json file where all other device ids connected to the supernode are recorded. Figure 6 illustrates the sequence of messages exchanged between the device, the Edge server of the device and the REST service.

FIGURE 6. Sequence Diagram of Initialization Phase

Request Payment and Check Incoming Payment

After the *Initialization Phase*, the initialized parking device will scan the area around it to detect any vehicles approaching it. When a vehicle approaches it, it will then send a *Request Payment*. A POST request containing the parked vehicle license plate number is sent to the URI API located on the web server. From the web server, it will collect the *Request Payment* data obtained from the database to publish a '0' value transaction containing the *Request Payment* message to the IOTA Full Node which will then be recorded or attached to the Tangle.

Check Incoming Payment will retrieve the transaction hash from its own wallet receiving address in Tangle using the 'findTransaction ()' function while the collected data is translated and written to .json file which records the transactions history. Upon receiving payment, the payment's source and transaction data are verified and recorded to a .json file. Finally, MAM's message containing the payment details and source of payment which is the vehicle number plate is sent to the Tangle. These MAM messages will be displayed in the application

to be viewed by the owner. *Request Payment* and *Check Incoming Payment* are executed by the parking device and the sequence diagram are shown in Figure 7.

Check Payment Request and Send Payment

After the vehicle selects and parks in the parking slot, it will carry out the *Check Payment Request*. The vehicle will collect the transaction hash from its own wallet receiving address at Tangle using the 'findTransaction ()' function while the collected data is translated and written to a .json file that records the transaction history. Upon receipt of the incoming payment request, the payment source and transaction data are verified and written to .json file and continue to send parking fee payment. Sending Payment will compile the payment data on the vehicle's Edge server and issue it to Tangle. After making a payment from your vehicle's shopping address, a new address is generated and an update is made to the database via the POST request to the REST API. The expense address must be renewed in each transaction because the more value transactions are made from the same address, the easier it is to get a personal key to the wallet using Brute Force or

Analytic Script, therefore the expense address cannot be used twice. Finally, a MAM message is then sent to Tangle regarding payment details and displayed in the vehicle owner application. *Check*

Payment Request and *Send Payment* are executed by the parking device and the sequence diagram are shown in Figure 8.

FIGURE 7. Sequence Diagram of *Request Payment* and *Check Incoming Payment*

FIGURE 8. Sequence Diagram of Check Payment Request and Send Payment

IoT Implementation

By implementing the edge centric IoT, data produced by the sensors in individual IoT nodes are decoded and translated on the Edge network through the sensor drivers, in this case the GPIO drivers found in the Pi. After that, these data are processed and stored in Edge local database. The data is then sent to the cloud and the IOTA network as shown in Figure 9. MQTT is used as a communication protocol for IoT implementation which is a light command protocol designed for embedded systems, sensors and mobile / web applications.

IoT devices such as parking device and AVs usually run and process several applications that perform various activities from different aspects and therefore will also publish and subscribe to variety of different topics. Therefore, it is more efficient that IoT devices open only one MQTT connection to the cloud rather than every application and every activity that connects to the cloud. This will cause latency and throughput problems during the transfer of these data.

Hence, the solution is to use local MQTT broker for the updates and data collections with the local MQTT clients in real-time as shown in Figure 10. Finally, the MQTT cloud platform which is the HiveMQ MQTT cloud is used to connect IoT

devices and applications from different networks to the HiveMQTT cloud broker shown in Figure 11.

FIGURE 9. Edge module

FIGURE 10. MQTT client to local Mosca MQTT broker connection

FIGURE 11. MQTT client to public MQTT broker Hivemq connection

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proof of Concept

A Proof of Concept payment system has been developed that establishes a DLT based M2M economy. This PoC shows a vehicle is parked in front of a parking device in a parking slot. Parking payment will be done autonomously by the vehicle and both the parking device and vehicle will be able verify and identify the entire process and source of the transactions, hence eliminating any form of human intervention in the process of payment.

When the parking device does not sense any vehicle within 10cm from it, the green LED will light up to indicate parking slot is empty as shown in Figure 12. When a vehicle is parked in front of the parking device which is within 10cm from it, the parking device will take a photo of the object and identify the vehicle by extracting the number plate of the vehicle using computer vision shown in Figure 13. Then, the payment process will begin in the server side which will be explained in the section below. Finally, the red LED will light up to indicate the parking slot is occupied as shown in Figure 14.

The web / mobile applications for the parking device and vehicle are developed and designed as shown in Figure 15-18 so that the owner of the respective parking device or vehicle will be able to check the balance in form of IOTA currency of their devices and the history of all transactions made by their devices. Google map API is integrated in the application that shows the location of the available parking devices as shown in Figure 19. The availability of the parking slots are updated in real-time using the MQTT protocol.

FIGURE 12. A Trigno™ Personal Monitor

FIGURE 13. A Trigno™ Personal Monitor

FIGURE 14. A Trigno™ Personal Monitor

FIGURE 15. Parking device application homepage

FIGURE 16. Parking device's balance and MAM stream

FIGURE 19. Available parking locations

FIGURE 17. Vehicle application homepage

FIGURE 18. vehicle's balance and MAM stream

Server-side Processes

First, the edge server log of the parking device prints the extracted number plate of vehicle received from the parking device through the MQTT protocol. Then, the edge server issues a *Request Payment* request to the web server at the same time recording the activity as a MAM message to the Tangle.

The web server log prints the compiled information of *Request Payment* upon receiving the request earlier, which contain the rate of parking fee, parking device's address and payment information that will be encrypted and sent as a 0 value transaction to the receiving wallet address of the parked vehicle.

The edge server log of vehicle will then prints the encrypted request payment information and decrypts them upon receiving the *Request Payment* transaction. Next, payment is made and the remaining balance of the vehicle is printed in the log at the same time recording the activity as a MAM message to the Tangle.

Finally, edge server log of the parking device prints the received payment made by the vehicle and the activity is recorded as a MAM message and sent to the Tangle. The owner of this parking device and vehicle will be able to access the MAM messages through their web / mobile application shown in Figure 16 and Figure 18. These server-side processes are recorded in the Figure 20.

FIGURE 20. Servers' log of payment processes

IOTA Protocol

To further analyze and examine the IOTA protocol, *Request Payment* transaction made by parking device to the receiving address of vehicle is used as an example. The transaction hash can be found in the log of web server in Figure 20. In a IOTA transaction, the transaction information is stored and encoded in a string of 2673 trytes length shown in Figure 21. In order to read this data, the client library function `iota.utils.transactionObject()` is used to decode the data and the result is shown in Figure 22. The decoded data shows the transaction objects with the properties shown in Table 1.

As previously mentioned, in IOTA there is no transaction fees. As such the process of making a

transaction is different from any existing DLT. The process in IOTA looks as follows(“Making a Transaction · IOTA Guide” n.d.):

Signing: Transaction inputs which is signed with a private key.

Tip Selection: MCMC tip selection algorithm is used to randomly select two tips, which will be referenced with the transaction made. (branchTransaction and trunkTransaction)

Proof of Work: In order to have the transaction accepted by the network, PoW is done which usually takes a few minutes on a modern pc. In this case, the parking device which is built on Raspberry Pi Zero W board takes approximately 10 minutes to complete this process.

After transaction process is completed, the trunkTransaction, branchTransaction and nonce of

Object	Format	Lenght(trytes)	Properties
hash	String	81	Unique hash of this transaction
signatureMessageFragment	String	2187	Message in Request Payment transaction that is encoded from ASCII to trytes
address	String	81	Address. In this case is an 'output' which is the receiving address of vehicle
value	Int		Value of transaction
timestamp	Int		Timestamp of transaction
currentIndex	Int		Index of this transaction in the bundle
lastIndex	Int		Total numbers of transactions in this bundle
bundle	String	81	Bundle hash. In this transaction is '0' because the value of transaction is '0'
trunkTransaction	String	81	Hash of first transaction approved with this transaction
branchTransaction	String	81	Hash of second transaction approved with this transaction
nonce	String	81	Nonce required for validating this transaction by Proof of Work.

FIGURE 23. Visualizer of Request Payment transaction

approving two other transactions and being approved by

another transaction

CONCLUSION

In order to establish a scalable, transparent and secure M2M economy, an alternative DLT called IOTA is used. Besides, edge centric IoT is preferred over the cloud centric IoT architecture as data are collected and processed at the edge first instead of simply aggregating data to the cloud. This ensures scalability of the IoT-AV ecosystem, reduced data traffic congestions and increased security of overall system. Next, a parking payment system for autonomous vehicle as a Proof of Concept (PoC) DLT based M2M economy is successfully designed and implemented. This is done by implementing IOTA library for enabling payment methods to

decentralized database called the Tangle and allow MAM stream to be accessible by devices and applications, using MQTT protocol to communicate between IoT devices with edge servers and designing a RESTful API to facilitate instructions and data between devices, web servers and system's database. Finally the properties of the IOTA transaction structure is examined and analysed by using the one of the PoC's transaction which is the *Request Payment* transaction. Additionally, from the decoded transaction object and visualizer, we are able to identify the trunkTransaction and branchTransaction which show that the *Request Payment* transaction has been successfully attached to the Tangle by approving two other transactions. This also shows the directed acyclic nature of the Tangle.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to take this opportunity to thank my supervisor, Prof. Ir. Dr. Mandeep Singh a/l Jit Singh for guiding me throughout this research. He guided me patiently when I faced any problems regarding to this research. I also want to thank my friends and course mates for being supportive and helpful in the process of finishing the research.

REFERENCES

Conoscenti, M., Vetro, A. & De Martin, J. C. 2016. Blockchain for the Internet of Things: A systematic literature review. *Proceedings of IEEE/ACS International Conference on Computer Systems and Applications, AICCSA* 0. doi:10.1109/AICCSA.2016.7945805

Corsaro, A. 2016. Cloudy, Foggy and Misty Internet of Things. doi:10.1145/2851553.2858661

- Gartner Identifies Top 10 Strategic IoT Technologies and Trends. (n.d.). <https://www.gartner.com/en/newsroom/press-releases/2018-11-07-gartner-identifies-top-10-strategic-iot-technologies-and-trends> [22 July 2020].
- GSMA. 2018. Opportunities and Use Cases for Distributed Ledger Technologies in IoT 42. Retrieved from <https://www.gsma.com/iot/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/Opportunities-and-Use-Cases-for-Distributed-Ledgers-in-IoT-f.pdf>
- Internet, T. & Intelligence, A. 2016. Beecham Research. *The Future of Retail Through the Internet of Things*. Retrieved from <https://www.intel.com/content/dam/www/public/us/en/documents/white-papers/future-retail-through-iot-paper.pdf>
- Making a Transaction · IOTA Guide. (n.d.). <https://domschiener.gitbooks.io/iota-guide/content/chapter1/how-to-make-a-transaction.html> [21 July 2020].
- Momtaz, P. P. 2020. Initial coin offerings. *PLoS ONE* 15(5). doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0233018
- ngrok - secure introspectable tunnels to localhost. (n.d.). <https://ngrok.com/product> [10 June 2020].
- OpenALPR Documentation — openalpr 2.7.102 documentation. (n.d.). <http://doc.openalpr.com/> [10 June 2020].
- Popov, S. 2018. The Tangle 和訳 1–26. Retrieved from https://iota.org/IOTA_Whitepaper.pdf
- Rauchs, M., Glidden, A., Gordon, B., Pieters, G. C., Recanatini, M., Rostand, F., Vagneur, K., et al. 2018. Distributed Ledger Technology Systems: A Conceptual Framework. *SSRN Electronic Journal* (August). doi:10.2139/ssrn.3230013
- Weisenberger, F. & de Knecht, F. 2019. DAG – A potential game changer in the field of M2M communication.
- Yeow, K., Gani, A., Ahmad, R. W., Rodrigues, J. J. P. C. & Ko, K. 2018. Decentralized Consensus for Edge-Centric Internet of Things: A Review, Taxonomy, and Research Issues. *IEEE Access* 6: 1513–1524. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2779263